

Incorporating Jumps in Valuation of Asian Option with Geometric Poisson Process

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Abstract

Traditional option pricing models often fail to account for abrupt movements in asset prices observed in real markets. In this work, we introduce a novel framework for incorporating jump processes into the valuation of Asian options by modeling the underlying asset using a Geometric Poisson process. We develop two distinct approaches: a computational method that leverages the Poisson probability mass function with Monte-Carlo integral approximation to account for discrete jumps, and a martingale-based method utilizing the two-dimensional Itô-Doebelin formula for processes with jumps. These methods offer both practical and theoretical tools for pricing options in markets subject to sudden discontinuities, enhancing the realism and flexibility of jump-diffusion models.

1 Introduction

The classical Black-Scholes framework [Black and Scholes, 1973], which models asset price dynamics using a continuous geometric Brownian motion, has been instrumental in the development of modern option pricing theory. However, empirical evidence strongly suggests that financial asset prices often exhibit sudden and discontinuous movements that cannot be captured by purely diffusive models. These abrupt changes, commonly referred to as jumps, are typically caused by events such as macroeconomic announcements, earnings surprises, or market shocks. As a result, models incorporating jump processes have gained increasing relevance for more accurate and robust pricing of financial derivatives.

In particular, the valuation of European and exotic options, such as Asian options, benefits from the inclusion of jump components. Asian options, whose payoffs depend on the average of the underlying asset over time, pose additional analytical challenges due to their path-dependent nature. Traditional methods often fall short in capturing both the discontinuous asset movements and the averaging feature simultaneously.

Motivated by these challenges, we propose a novel approach to model asset prices using a Geometric Poisson process, which captures discrete jumps in a mathematically tractable manner. This modeling choice facilitates the integration of jump risk into the valuation of European and Asian options.

We focus on Asian options due to their significant practical relevance in financial markets, particularly in the pricing and hedging of commodities and energy derivatives. Unlike standard European options, Asian options depend on the average price of the underlying asset over a specified period, which makes them less sensitive to price manipulation and short-term volatility. This averaging feature introduces a path dependency that presents unique analytical challenges, especially when combined with jump processes. By addressing these complexities, our work aims to provide more realistic and robust pricing techniques that better align with real-world market behavior.

Motivated by the approach taken by Shreve [2004] to evaluate the European option under jumps, we develop two complementary methodologies for option pricing under this framework. The first is a computational approach that directly incorporates the Poisson mass function of the jump process to construct the option

value through probabilistic aggregation over jump realizations. It also uses Monte-Carlo integral approximation for estimating the integral present in the Asian Call Option Payoff. This technique provides an intuitive and implementable method of handling jump risk.

The second method is rooted in martingale theory and leverages the two-dimensional Itô-Doeblin formula for processes with jumps. By applying this generalized stochastic calculus framework, we derive a partial differential-integral equation governing the option price evolution under jump dynamics. This martingale approach provides theoretical clarity and aligns with arbitrage-free pricing principles.

Together, these methods offer both practical and theoretical avenues for capturing jump effects in option pricing, contributing to the advancement of models that better reflect real market behaviors.

2 Related Works

In classical option theory, asset prices were modeled by continuous diffusions, but [Merton \[1976\]](#) introduced a jump-diffusion model to allow sudden price shifts. This line of work produced many tractable variants. [Bates \[1996\]](#) combined Merton’s jumps with Heston-style stochastic volatility. More generally, jump processes and exponential-Lévy models capture observed leptokurtic and skew features of returns. For example, daily return kurtosis is more naturally explained by jumps than by diffusion models [[Kou, 2002](#)]. Jumps also naturally generate the volatility smiles observed in option markets.

Beyond these classics, a broad class of infinite-activity Lévy jump models (e.g., Variance Gamma, Normal Inverse Gaussian, CGMY) has been used in option valuation to capture heavy tails and smiles. These models often fit market option prices better than Black–Scholes. For instance, [Yilmaz and Hekimoglu \[2022\]](#) calibrate VG and NIG jumps on index options and find jump models (especially NIG) outperform Black–Scholes in pricing accuracy. Recent research also explores time-varying jump intensity: regime-switching and self-exciting (Hawkes) jumps have been proposed. Advanced numerical and transform methods (FFT, CTMC, COS, etc.) enable fast pricing under very general jump specifications. These flexible jump frameworks help explain volatility smiles in practice.

Exotic derivatives have also been studied under jump frameworks. [Schoutens \[2004\]](#) surveyed pricing of barrier, lookback and related exotics in exponential-Lévy models. Kou’s model, for example, yields (semi-)analytic formulas for barrier and lookback options [[Kou, 2002](#)]. More recently, [Brignone and Sgarra \[2020\]](#) show how to price Asian options when jumps follow a Hawkes process. [Kirkby and Nguyen \[2020\]](#) developed a unified Fourier/CTMC method to price Asian and other path-dependent payoffs under a wide class of jump-diffusion models. Collectively, these advances extend jump-based valuation tools for European and exotic options.

[Shreve \[2004\]](#) presents a rigorous framework for valuing European options under jump processes by extending the classical models to accommodate discontinuous asset price movements. The approach introduces two primary methodologies. The first is a martingale-based technique that reformulates the pricing problem within an equivalent risk-neutral measure, ensuring that the discounted asset price—including jump components—remains a martingale. The second is a computational method that explicitly accounts for the jump structure using the Poisson distribution to model the number of jumps over time. This approach constructs the option value as a series expansion, where each term corresponds to the expected value of the option conditional on a specific number of jumps having occurred. Both methods converge to the same valuation and offer complementary perspectives—analytical and numerical—on the pricing of options in markets exhibiting jump behavior.

3 Preliminaries

Asian Option An Asian option is a financial derivative whose payoff depends on the average value of the underlying asset price over a specified time interval. This averaging period may span the entire duration from the option’s initiation to its expiration, or it may commence at a later time and continue until maturity. The averaging itself can be performed using either continuous or discrete sampling schemes.

In the case of continuous sampling, the average is computed as:

$$\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T S(t) dt,$$

where $S(t)$ denotes the asset price at time t , and T is the time to maturity.

Alternatively, for discrete sampling, the average is taken over specific time points:

$$\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m S(t_i),$$

where $0 < t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_m = T$.

We augment the state $S(t)$ by defining a second process,

$$Y(t) = \int_0^t S(u) du \tag{1}$$

The stochastic differential equation for $Y(t)$ is thus

$$dY(t) = S(t)dt \tag{2}$$

The main motivation for designing option payoffs based on average prices is to reduce the potential for market manipulation near the option's expiration. Averaging mitigates the influence of short-term price fluctuations, making the option more robust to strategic price distortions. The payoff for the Asian Call Option is given as follows,

$$V(T) = \left(\frac{1}{T} Y(T) - K \right)^+ \tag{3}$$

Where K is the strike price of the option. Unlike standard European options, Asian options do not generally admit closed-form pricing solutions. Consequently, numerical methods such as Monte Carlo simulation are commonly employed to estimate their values.

Geometric Poisson Process Let $\{N(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$ be a standard Poisson process with constant intensity $\tilde{\lambda} > 0$ (the risk neutral intensity). That is,

$$P(N(t) = n) = e^{-\tilde{\lambda}t} \frac{(\tilde{\lambda}t)^n}{n!}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \tag{4}$$

We define a *geometric Poisson process* $\{S(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$ by

$$S(t) = S(0)e^{(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)t} (\sigma + 1)^{N(t)} \tag{5}$$

Here we use the Geometric Poisson Process to model the asset price.

Monte-Carlo Integral Approximation Monte Carlo integral approximation estimates the integral

$$I = \int_a^b f(x) dx$$

over a bounded domain $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ by drawing n i.i.d. samples $x_i \sim \mathcal{U}(a, b)$ (the Uniform Distribution), and computing the unbiased estimator

$$\hat{I}_N = \frac{b-a}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(x_i). \tag{6}$$

Its root-mean-square error decays as $O(n^{-1/2})$.

Valuation of Asian Option There must exist some function $C(t, x, y)$ such that the Asian call price is given as

$$C(t, S(t), Y(t)) = \mathbb{E}\left[e^{-r(T-t)}\left(\frac{1}{T}Y(T) - K\right)^+ \mid \mathcal{F}(t)\right] = \mathbb{E}[e^{-r(T-t)}V(T) \mid \mathcal{F}(t)]$$

Recall *Theorem 7.5.1* from [Shreve, 2004]

Theorem 3.1. *The Asian call price function $c(t, x, y)$ satisfies, for $0 \leq t < T$, $x \geq 0$, $y \in \mathbb{R}$,*

$$C_t(t, x, y) + r x C_x(t, x, y) + x C_y(t, x, y) + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 x^2 C_{xx}(t, x, y) = r C(t, x, y), \quad (7)$$

with boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} C(t, 0, y) &= e^{-r(T-t)}(y - K)^+, & 0 \leq t < T, y \in \mathbb{R}, \\ \lim_{y \rightarrow -\infty} C(t, x, y) &= 0, & 0 \leq t < T, x \geq 0, \\ V(T, x, y) &= (y - K)^+, & x \geq 0, y \in \mathbb{R}. \end{aligned}$$

Our objective is to use the geometric Poisson process in place of the geometric Brownian motion and provide a result similar to the above one incorporating the jumps. For that we need a particular tool from [Shreve, 2004] (*Theorem 11.5.4* to be precise) as follows,

Theorem 3.2 (Two-dimensional Itô-Doeblin formula for processes with jumps). *Let $X_1(t)$ and $X_2(t)$ be jump processes, and let $f(t, X_1, X_2)$ be a function whose first and second partial derivatives appearing in the following formula are defined and continuous. Then for $0 \leq t$,*

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, X_1(t), X_2(t)) &= f(0, X_1(0), X_2(0)) + \int_0^t f_t(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) ds \\ &+ \int_0^t f_{x_1}(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) dX_1^c(s) + \int_0^t f_{x_2}(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) dX_2^c(s) \\ &+ \int_0^t f_{x_1, x_1}(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) dX_1^c(s) dX_1^c(s) \\ &+ \int_0^t f_{x_1, x_2}(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) dX_1^c(s) dX_2^c(s) \\ &+ \int_0^t f_{x_2, x_2}(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) dX_2^c(s) dX_2^c(s) \\ &+ \sum_{0 < s \leq t} \left[f(s, X_1(s), X_2(s)) - f(s, X_1(s^-), X_2(s^-)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

We use this in one of our main results for finding the valuation of asian option under geometric poisson process with jumps.

4 Main Results

In this section we propose two different methods to evaluate the value of the Asian Call Option as mentioned before.

4.1 Computational Method

We begin by stating and proving the following lemma, which underpins the computational approach to pricing options with jump risk. This result enables the explicit decomposition of the asset price process into a series of discrete jumps governed by the Poisson distribution. By characterizing the probability of observing a specific number of jumps within a given time horizon, the lemma allows us to compute the option price as a weighted sum over possible jump scenarios.

Theorem 4.1. For $0 \leq t < T$, the risk-neutral price of a European call option with strike price K and maturity T is given by:

$$V(t) = \tilde{\mathbb{E}} \left[e^{-r(T-t)} \left(\frac{1}{T} Y(T) - K \right)^+ \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right],$$

where $V(t) = C(t, S(t))$ and:

$$\begin{aligned} C(t, x) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[e^{-r(T-t)} (x e^{(T-t+1)(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)} - K)^+ \right] e^{-\bar{\lambda}(2T_i-t)} \\ &+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[e^{-r(T-t)} (x e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^k e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(T-t)} - K)^+ \right] e^{-\bar{\lambda}(T_i-t)} \frac{\lambda^k T_i^k}{k!} e^{-\bar{\lambda}T_i} \\ &+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[e^{r(T-t)} (x e^{(T-t+1)(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^j - K)^+ \right] \frac{\lambda^j (T_i-t)^j}{j!} e^{-\bar{\lambda}(2T_i-t)} \\ &+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[e^{r(T-t)} (x e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^k e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(T-t)} (\sigma+1)^j - K)^+ \right] \frac{\lambda^j (T_i-t)^j}{j!} e^{-\bar{\lambda}(T_i-t)} \frac{\lambda^k T_i^k}{k!} e^{-\bar{\lambda}T_i} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

And $T_i \sim \mathcal{U}(t, T)$

Proof. Recall using (5),

$$\begin{aligned} S(T) &= S(0) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^{N(T)} \\ S(t) &= S(0) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^{N(t)} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, using theorem 3.1 we obtain,

$$C(t, S(t), Y(t)) = V(T) = \tilde{\mathbb{E}} \left[e^{-r(T-t)} \left(\frac{1}{T-t} \int_t^T S(u) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(u-t)} (\sigma+1)^{N(u)-N(t)} du - K \right)^+ \right] \quad (10)$$

In order to proceed further we need to compute the integral, which is basically the area under an Ito process. Instead of solving it analytically, we propose an alternate numerical way of estimating this integral using Monte-Carlo integral approximation.

Hence using (6) we attain,

$$\int_t^T S(u) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(u-t)} (\sigma+1)^{N(u)-N(t)} du = (T-t) \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n S(T_i) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(T_i-t)} (\sigma+1)^{N(T_i)-N(t)}$$

Where $T_i \in [t, T] \quad \forall \quad i = 1(1)n$. And we also know by the property of Poisson jump processes (4) that,

$$P(N(T_i) - N(t) = j) = \frac{\lambda^j (T_i-t)^j}{j!} e^{-\bar{\lambda}(T_i-t)}$$

Now, combining this with the last expression, we can express (10) as,

$$\begin{aligned} C(t, S(t), Y(t)) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[e^{-r(T-t)} (S(T_i) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(T-t)} - K)^+ \right] e^{-\bar{\lambda}(T_i-t)} \\ &+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[e^{r(T-t)} (S(T_i) e^{(r-\bar{\lambda}\sigma)(T-t)} (\sigma+1)^j - K)^+ \right] \frac{\lambda^j (T_i-t)^j}{j!} e^{-\bar{\lambda}(T_i-t)} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, our final expression for $C(t, x)$ using (4) again is,

$$\begin{aligned}
C(t, x) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[e^{-r(T-t)} \left(x e^{(T-t+1)(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)} - K \right)^+ \right] e^{-\tilde{\lambda}(2T_i-t)} \\
&+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[e^{-r(T-t)} \left(x e^{(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^k e^{(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)(T-t)} - K \right)^+ \right] e^{-\tilde{\lambda}(T_i-t)} \frac{\lambda^k T_i^k}{k!} e^{-\tilde{\lambda}T_i} \\
&+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[e^{r(T-t)} \left(x e^{(T-t+1)(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^j - K \right)^+ \right] \frac{\lambda^j (T_i-t)^j}{j!} e^{-\tilde{\lambda}(2T_i-t)} \\
&+ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[e^{r(T-t)} \left(x e^{(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)} (\sigma+1)^k e^{(r-\tilde{\lambda}\sigma)(T-t)} (\sigma+1)^j - K \right)^+ \right] \frac{\lambda^j (T_i-t)^j}{j!} e^{-\tilde{\lambda}(T_i-t)} \frac{\lambda^k T_i^k}{k!} e^{-\tilde{\lambda}T_i}
\end{aligned}$$

where $T_i \sim \mathcal{U}(t, T)$ □

4.2 Martingale Method

In the martingale framework, we rely on the following lemma, which provides the analytical foundation for incorporating jumps into stochastic differential representations. Specifically, the lemma applies the two-dimensional Itô-Doeblin formula to a process involving both the asset price and a path-dependent term such as the time integral of the asset. This result is crucial for deriving the evolution equation for the option price under jump dynamics, ensuring consistency with arbitrage-free pricing theory.

Theorem 4.2. *The call price $C(t, x)$ of satisfies the stochastic differential equation:*

$$\begin{aligned}
&-rC(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_t(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_s(u, S(u), Y(u))(r - \tilde{\lambda}\sigma) \\
&+ C_y(u, S(u), Y(u))S(u) + \tilde{\lambda}(C(u, (\sigma+1)S(u-), Y(u-)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-))) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Proof. Recall that for an Asian Option with jumps contributed by the Geometric Poisson Process, the following properties hold:

$$dS^c(t) = (r - \tilde{\lambda}\sigma)S(t) dt$$

$$\Delta S^c(t) = S(t) - S(t^-) = \sigma S(t^-)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta Y(t) &= Y(t) - Y(t^-) \\
&= \int_0^t S(u) du - \lim_{v \rightarrow t^-} \int_0^v S(u) du \\
&= \int_0^t S(u) du - \int_0^t S(u) du \\
&= 0
\end{aligned}$$

$$dY(t) = S(t) dt$$

The last expression holds from (2) and $S^c(t)$ denotes the continuous part of S . Essentially $Y^c(t) = Y(t)$ since S has jump discontinuities so Y is continuous by its own definition. Also, from expression (2), we arrive at the following,

$$\begin{aligned}
dY(t)dY(t) &= (S(t))^2(dt)^2 = 0 \\
dY(t)dS^c(t) &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

We recall that for an Asian Option, (1) suggests that $Y(t) = \int_0^t S(u)du$
Using theorem 3.2 (The 2-dimensional Ito-Doeblin Formula for Jumps),

$$\begin{aligned}
& e^{-rt}C(t, S(t), Y(t)) \\
&= C(0, S(0), Y(0)) + \int_0^t e^{-ru} [-rC(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_t(u, S(u), Y(u))] du \\
&+ \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_s(u, S(u), Y(u)) dS^c(u) + \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_y(u, S(u), Y(u)) dY(u) \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_{ss}(u, S(u), Y(u)) d\langle S^c(u), S^c(u) \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_{yy}(u, S(u), Y(u)) d\langle Y(u), Y(u) \rangle \\
&+ \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_{sy}(u, S(u), Y(u)) d\langle S^c(u), Y(u) \rangle + \sum_{0 < u \leq t} e^{-ru} [C(u, S(u), Y(u)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-))] \\
&= C(0, S(0), Y(0)) + \int_0^t e^{-ru} [-rC(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_t(u, S(u), Y(u))] du + \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_y(u, S(u), Y(u)) S^c(u) du \\
&+ \int_0^t e^{-ru} C_s(u, S(u), Y(u)) dS^c(u) + \sum_{0 < u \leq t} e^{-ru} [C(u, S(u), Y(u)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-))] \\
&= C(0, S(0), Y(0)) \\
&+ \int_0^t e^{-ru} \left[-rC(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_t(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_s(u, S(u), Y(u))(r - \tilde{\lambda}\sigma) + C_y(u, S(u), Y(u))S^c(u) \right] du \\
&+ \sum_{0 < u \leq t} e^{-ru} [C(u, (\sigma + 1)S(u-), Y(u-)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-))] \\
&= C(0, S(0), Y(0)) \\
&+ \int_0^t e^{-ru} \left[-rC(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_t(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_s(u, S(u), Y(u))(r - \tilde{\lambda}\sigma) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + C_y(u, S(u), Y(u))S(u) + \tilde{\lambda}(C(u, (\sigma + 1)S(u-), Y(u-)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-))) \right] du \\
&+ \int_0^t e^{-ru} \left[C(u, (\sigma + 1)S(u-), Y(u-)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-)) \right] d\tilde{M}(u)
\end{aligned}$$

We know the L.H.S is a martingale and also the third term of the R.H.S is a martingale as $\tilde{M}(u)$ is a martingale and the integrand is left-continuous. Therefore, in order for the second term to also be a martingale, we must have the integrand equal to zero.

Hence, we obtain the stochastic differential equation (11),

$$\begin{aligned}
& -rC(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_t(u, S(u), Y(u)) + C_s(u, S(u), Y(u))(r - \tilde{\lambda}\sigma) \\
& + C_y(u, S(u), Y(u))S(u) + \tilde{\lambda}(C(u, (\sigma + 1)S(u-), Y(u-)) - C(u, S(u-), Y(u-))) = 0
\end{aligned}$$

Solving (11) gives us the value of the option $C(t, S(t), Y(t))$. □

5 Conclusion

Several significant contributions have been made in the past to incorporate jump processes into the valuation of European and Asian options. These models typically aim to capture the discontinuities and abrupt changes observed in financial markets that cannot be adequately explained by continuous diffusion-based frameworks alone. The inclusion of jumps allows for a more realistic modeling of asset price dynamics, which improves the accuracy and robustness of option pricing methodologies.

In this work, we present a novel approach to the incorporation of jump processes in the pricing of Asian options. Specifically, we propose modeling the asset price dynamics using a Geometric Poisson process. A similar method was proposed by [Shreve, 2004] for valuation of European option with jumps. This choice enables the modeling of sudden discrete changes in asset prices while preserving tractability within the pricing framework.

To support this modeling choice, we introduce two distinct methodologies. The first is a computational approach that utilizes the probability mass function of the Poisson process to approximate the contribution of jumps to the overall option value. This technique allows for a discrete and interpretable approximation of the price evolution under jump dynamics. The second is a martingale-based approach grounded in arbitrage-free pricing theory. By constructing an appropriate risk-neutral measure under which the discounted asset price becomes a martingale, we derive expressions for the option price that account for both the diffusive and jump components of the asset process.

Together, these methodologies provide a rigorous and flexible framework for the valuation of options in the presence of jumps, and they offer alternative perspectives for practitioners and researchers interested in robust pricing under realistic market conditions.

As part of future work, we aim to conduct a detailed experimental evaluation of the proposed pricing methodologies to assess their empirical performance and robustness under various market conditions. This will involve implementing the models on real and simulated market data, comparing accuracy, computational efficiency, and sensitivity to parameter changes. Additionally, we plan to extend our framework to accommodate more complex exotic derivatives such as compound, chooser, rainbow, and cliquet options. These options involve multiple layers of path- or state-dependence, and incorporating jumps into their valuation presents both analytical and computational challenges. Addressing these will help further generalize and validate our approach for a broader class of financial instruments.

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